

EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs (Final protocol)

*Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural
Innovation*

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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List of Acronyms & Abbreviations in D3.2

Abbreviation	Description
EPIC-WE	Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments
TH	Triple Helix
QH	Quadruple Helix
DBR	Design-Based Research and Innovation
LL	Living Lab
CLL	Cultural Living Lab
HEI	Higher Education Institution
CI	Creative Industry
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institution
YC	Youth Citizens
QH Cultural Hub	Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam
EPIC-WE CH	EPIC-WE Cultural Hub
EPIC-WE CGJ	EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam
EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem	EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem

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Executive Summary

0. Executive Summary

This report presents the foundational principles, along with practical sector, glocal, and local dimensions, of the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs.

By summarising the theoretical frameworks of the Triple Helix (TH), Quadruple Helix Ecosystem, and Living Lab model introduced in D3.1, Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation (2024), the D3.2, Protocol 1 transforms these concepts into EPIC-WE researched foundational requirements and principles for the macro-level design of the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs that serve as implemented, tested, and evaluated models for partners to engage in cross-sector co-creation of research and innovation in culture and cultural heritage, practised through transformative partnerships and meeting(s) in the middle.

A critical aspect of the development of the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs is the joint and iterative materialisation of shared models, principles, and practices. With the present D3.2, Protocol 1(2025) here, the EPIC-WE project makes significant strides in developing and refining the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs initially presented in D3.1, Protocol 1 (2024) and through the project's first round of Design-Based Research interventions. The principles and models presented here define and describe how to connect diverse sectors, partners, and participants in co-creating innovation and research across European cultural heritage sites. The concept of 'meeting in the middle' is central to forming such 'epic we' transformative partnerships in cultural research and innovation.

Importantly, D3.2, 'Protocol 1 on Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation: EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and QH Cultural Hubs (final report)' combines the foundational principles for the development, implementation, and operationalisation of the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem (9 principles) and Cultural Hubs (6 principles) to its core contribution: the EPIC-WE model for QH Cultural Hubs and its 2 x 4 requirements (see below). Taken together, these constitute the macro-level contribution of the EPIC-WE project. As a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action, the content of this report has been evaluated, iterated, and reinforced by the knowledge and experiences produced during the project. This includes the EPIC-WE Prisma2020 Systematic Literature Review, the review and research included in the D3.1 Protocol 1, the project's Research Protocol and research results, its 12 Design-Based Research interventions, capacity building with experts and advisory board members, the project's research publications and presentations along with its cross-sector cross-hub activities carried out within and across the EPIC-WE Work Packages to ensure its innovations are properly and thoroughly grounded in both research and practice.

Looking towards the future, extending D3.1, Protocol 1 with D3.2, Protocol 1 will lead to further conceptualisations, implementations, explorations, and evaluations of the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs in the remaining project period (2025-2026).

Overall, the EPIC-WE project outcomes of the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs offer a significant contribution to the field of cultural innovation in cross-sector partnerships. The project's emphasis on cultural co-creation, cross-sector collaboration, transformative partnerships, meeting in the middle, open knowledge sharing, and empowered participation results in a robust model for cross-sector cultural research and innovation presented in this report.

Below are listed the 9 foundational principles for Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems and the 6 foundational principles for Cultural Hubs that together result in the model and its 2 x 4 requirements for QH Cultural Hubs. These principles, models, and requirements are – along with important sector, glocal, and local dimensions, presented in the different sections of this report.

Foundational Principles for Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems

- 1 Co-creation and inclusive innovation
- 2 Interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration
- 3 Sustainability and empowered participation
- 4 Open knowledge sharing and transparency
- 5 Mutual trust and shared values in innovation
- 6 Curious, creative, and collective practices
- 7 Knowledge hybridity through partnerships across domains and sectors
- 8 Generative friction as a driver of epistemic and cultural transformation
- 9 Evaluation and culture-based decision-making

Foundational Principles for Cultural Hubs

- 1 Democratised Cultural Innovation by Including Citizens and Users as Core Partners in the Cultural Hub
- 2 Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation
- 3 Institute meetings in the middle
- 4 Practice co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s)
- 5 Develop real-world, real-life Cultural Hubs
- 6 Advance empowered participation in culture

The EPIC-WE model for the Quadruple Helix

1

Requirement 1: Include citizens as equal partners

In the development of the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, citizens play a central and critical role.

In the QH:

- **citizens are positioned as valued co-inventors** of their desired cultural products and futures
- **citizens are included as central research and innovation helix partner** to enhance the credibility, authenticity, cultural value, and benefits of its research & innovations

2

Requirement 2: Innovation through democratic & participatory processes

Formation of the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem is distinctly visible in the configuration of equal rights, roles, and responsibilities.

In the QH:

- there is an **equal distribution** of helix partners from CIs, CHIs, and HEIs with equal representation and rights.
- each partner is to be acknowledged and involved as **co-researcher, co-designer, co-innovator, and co-practitioner**.
- all partners **bring with them their own domain and expertise**, positioned as equally indispensable for and usable for all and for the research & innovation process.

The EPIC-WE model for the Quadruple Helix

3 Requirement 3: Cross-sectorial collaboration within transformative partnerships

Within the EPIC-WE QH, partners work together in close and continuous cross-sectorial co-creation to develop transformative QH partnerships and joint practices in cultural innovation.

- **On the macro level:** In order to think and talk together, the QH partners take joint decisions, collaborate on shared aims, objectives and outcomes and establish a common vocabulary and understanding.
- **On the meso level:** In order to be and act together, the QH form local hubs that meet monthly to ensure joint development of principles and protocols for cultural innovation
- **On the micro level:** In order to operationalise 'cultural innovations' through concrete everyday practices, the QH co-organise events and activities where all helix partners meet in the middle to test and evaluate cultural innovation formats, methods and processes.

4 Cultivating Mode 3 cultural knowledge & innovation cultures

The EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem aims towards reciprocal value creation. It should create both value for each individual helix partner and value creation for the combined helices as they join forces in the middle:

- A QH has **internal tensions and differences** when it comes to what counts as good knowledge, methods, practices, outcomes, and values.
- Consequently, the **whole should be greater than the sum of its parts** and be something partners cannot accomplish on their own. Otherwise, it is not worth the effort.
- **If any helix domain were excluded, the aimed-for cultural innovation would become impossible.** Only through the co-existence, co-evolution, and co-specialisation of the four domains, will cultural innovation in Cultural Hubs become possible.

The EPIC-WE model for Cultural Hubs

1 Requirement 1: Initiate Living Labs as QH transformer

Cultural Hubs are based on Living Labs principles. They transform the QH ecosystem into ‘everyday practices’ by bringing together diverse partners in culture and engaging them in real-world on the ground practices.

The goal of the Cultural Hub is **to form an ‘epic we’** that can carry out QH research and innovation:

- First, by facilitating a **‘de-centring’** of pre-existing sector-confined ways of knowing, doing and being
- Second, by enabling a **‘centring’** of new modes of collective and co-creative knowing, doing and being by meeting in the middle and thinking ‘other-wise’ within the Cultural Hub

2 Requirement 2: Set up Living Labs as cultural meeting places

- Cultural Hubs are conducive cultural environments and meeting places characterised by **‘communal ownership’** through co-operative operations & democratic participation
- For this to happen, QH partners must be ready to **‘meet each other halfway’ and leave behind** preconceptions and taken-for-granted knowledges, methods, and practices.

However, meeting the other(s) halfway is hard work to **‘embrace the culturally alien’** through continuously stabilising what is culturally unstable and destabilising what is culturally stable through collectively reimagining, reconfiguring, and revitalising new culture(s) in the middle.

The EPIC-WE model for Cultural Hubs

3 Requirement 3: Inhabit Living Labs as vibrant cultural homes

- **Cultural Hubs are ‘cultural homes’** for the coming together of the QH partners. They function as vibrant in vivo cultural environments.
- This requires **real-world, real-life sites of culture** wherein cultural practices naturally unfold as part of everyday cultural life. This could be museums, public spaces, libraries, cultural centres, cultural heritage sites, creative industries or other ‘living cultures’ within which the Cultural Hub can find a home and unfold.
- However, **the idea is not to ‘overpower’** or assimilate the existing cultural ecosystem, but to ideate and co-design cultural transformation with present/future sites and inhabitants.

4 Requirement 4: Practice Living Labs for empowered participation in culture

- The goal of the **Cultural Hubs is to provide environments for empowered participation** – collectively and individually. To position each QH partner as an indispensable and equal contributor within the Cultural Hub.
- **Cultural Hubs flourish when their QH partners flourish** and feel ‘at home’ respected and acknowledged – this is what Cultural Hubs are to be evaluated on.
- The QH partnership – and the Cultural Hub – **must resonate with cultural curiosity, creative imagination, empowered agency, and valued communality** to make sense - especially when measured against the efforts, tensions, complexities, challenges and compromises each QH sector and partner is confronted with in the middle.
- This is also what the EPIC-WE acronym stands for: ***Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments.***

Introduction

01

1. Introduction

1.1 The EPIC-WE project

EPIC-WE (Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments) is a Horizon Europe-funded project (2023-2026) aiming to empower youth citizens to participate in shaping European Culture and their own futures by 'imagining, creating and exchanging cultural values and heritage through game-making'. It explores and introduces new models for cultural innovation, collaboration, and empowered participation. To achieve this, EPIC-WE develops and iteratively tests and evaluates the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem (EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem), along with EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs (EPIC-WE CHs) and EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams (EPIC-WE CGJs), through 12 interventions across three European sites. The ambition of the project is to contribute a transferable framework for youth citizens (YCs), cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), and higher education institutions (HEIs) to work together as partners in cultural innovation and game-making as a new form of culture-making.

EPIC-WE brings together four different partner types – HEIs, CIs, CHIs, and YCs – to form new transformative cultural partnerships through close collaboration and co-creation. Each partner type represents a distinctive societal domain with its own knowledge, methods, and cultures – i.e., research/education (HEI), games/creative industries (CI), cultural heritage/museums (CHI), and citizenship/the public (YC). These four domains or sectors 'meet in the middle' to collaborate and develop more equal, co-creative, and empowered partnerships for future cross-sector cultural collaboration and innovation. As such, the EPIC-WE project consortium is itself configured as a Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, bringing together leading research, cultural and creative sector partners to invite YCs as a fourth helix partner in the ecosystem and take up practices of game-making as culture-making in CGJs and collaboration with the other three helix partners in each of the three QH Cultural Hubs in Aarhus (Denmark), Hilversum (Netherlands), and Óbidos (Portugal).

EPIC-WE engages in CGJs to create games through and for culture using cultural heritage and European values while engaging cultural or societal issues. The project explores this approach's potential to strengthen European values, cultural belonging, and empowered participation. Through cultural game-making activities, EPIC-WE aims to equip YCs with cultural-creative imagination and opportunities to engage in cultural and societal challenges with curiosity, creativity, agency, and imagination – what we in the project call Empowered Participation.

The aim is to empower and extend the helix partners' cultural and civil roles and societal position through practising transformative partnerships 'in the middle'. It advocates for partners in research/education (HEI), games/creative industries (CI), cultural heritage/museums (CHI), and citizenship/the public (YC) to join forces and work together through real-world everyday events and practices and establish new forms of transformative cross-sector interconnected partnerships in cultural research and innovation.

To achieve this, EPIC-WE is carried out as a Design-Based Research and Innovation (DBR) project across three QH Cultural Hubs, where the four helices co-operate and co-create, and through this, develop, implement, and evaluate the proposed innovations on the macro level (QH Cultural Hubs, meso level (Cultural Game Jams), and micro level (games through/for culture). The EPIC-WE framework on the macro, meso, and micro levels specifies how CHI, CI, HEI, and YC can work together as partners in cultural-creative innovation and transformation.

1.2. Development of the EPIC-WE macro-level framework

Partners in the EPIC-WE project work with lead beneficiary Aarhus University to develop and implement the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, QH Cultural Hubs, and Cultural Game Jams. This work has been initiated with the iterative development and dissemination of concept notes on Cultural Hubs, research publications, capacity-building webinars and workshops and the continued research of their instalments within the project. Throughout the process, the EPIC-WE partners, Executive Board, Advisory Board and experts have been invited to discuss, comment, reflect, co-create, and substantiate the core EPIC-WE innovations under development. In developing the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs (Protocol 1), a dedicated group of EPIC-WE partners and participants have constructed and designed these to be tested and evaluated through Design-Based Research (DBR). In the process, relevant task partners, work package partners, and consortium partners are invited to reflect, comment, revise, and reinforce these developments.

The first round of DBR 'Design and Construction' of the EPIC-WE macro level innovations (2023-2024) can be accessed in the deliverable D3.1 Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation that was evaluated and approved without reservation by the European Commission and Expert Evaluators during the project's periodic reporting (2024). In the D3.1, Protocol 1, the research grounding underlying the design and construction of the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation System and QH Cultural Hubs can also be found. Following this, the D3.1 Protocol 1 has been tested and evaluated through the first six EPIC-WE interventions, and the outcome of this research and innovation process has been disseminated in research publications – e.g. in Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. (2024). Meeting in the middle: Cultural co-creation, transformative partnerships, and ecosystems for public good. Educational Philosophy and Theory, 1-16 as well as developed, presented, and discussed through multiple conference talks and invited keynotes such as ECGBL 2024, University Future Festival 2024 and elsewhere, as well as through engaging with leading experts through the EPIC-WE Capacity Building Webinar and Workshop Series (2024-2025).

To further secure its research grounding, the report also draws on findings from the executed PRISMA2020 systematic literature review State of the Art in game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens carried out as part of the EPIC-WE project.

Furthermore, as part of the task and the general conceptualisation and practice of the different QH Cultural Hubs in EPIC-WE, the development of the deliverable D3.2, Protocol 1 incorporates collaborative insights, findings from research and innovation, and cross-cultural reflections produced through local analyses (T4.3), glocal analyses (T2.4), consortium feedback and feedforward sessions (T3.4), international hub meetings and workshops (T4.1), and several in-progress and under publication research and dissemination publications and presentations.

The consortium continues this work through the second round of DBR 'Design and Construction' of the EPIC-WE macro level innovations (2024-2025) to further conceptualise, evaluate, and iterate the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hub through the integration of the above and other research and innovation results created through the first full DBR round of the project (2023-2025). The result of this process is the present deliverable D3.2, Protocol 1 that you find here. You can also find a synthesised presentation of these results in the deliverable D3.3 "Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams, and Games through & for Culture: Report on Insights from the Design and Construction of Ecosystems and Game Jams" (2025).

1.3. Summary of the D3.1 Protocol 1

The EPIC-WE project focuses on constructing, implementing, and refining a Quadruple Helix (QH) ecosystem to promote empowered participation in cultural innovation. Protocol 1 of D3.1 outlines how this ecosystem integrates cultural industries (CIs), cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), higher education institutions (HEIs), and youth citizens (YCs) across three European sites: Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos. By creating collaborative spaces where these sectors 'meet in the middle', EPIC-WE establishes interwoven partnerships that transcend individual domains and foster structural transformations in cultural innovation. Central to this approach is the adaptation of QH principles and Mode 3 knowledge creation, which emphasises co-creation, democratic engagement, and the mutual adaptation and creation of knowledge cultures and practices. Through iterative development, this QH framework guides the creation of QH Cultural Hubs (CHs), cultural game jams (CGJs), and game-making as culture-making processes, fostering innovations that reflect shared European values and revitalise cultural heritage.

The project envisions a macro-level QH ecosystem that facilitates cross-sector collaboration while accommodating its domains' unique knowledge cultures and practices—culture, cultural heritage, and game-making. By enacting this model in practice, EPIC-WE partners iteratively refine the framework to establish the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem – which is further detailed and elaborated in the D3.1 Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation. This ecosystem empowers cultural participation and co-creation mechanisms, enabling diverse partners to collectively shape new cultural futures. The project materialises and enacts the QH ecosystem by constructing and operationalising QH Cultural Hubs as spaces for collaborative innovation.

The D3.1, Protocol 1, presents the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and Cultural Hubs, outlining their theoretical foundations, guiding principles, and practical applications. The report introduces and describes QH Ecosystems and lists their underlying principles derived from research and practice. The QH ecosystem and its principles are then adapted to target and be tailored to QH cultural innovation. Moreover, Protocol 1 introduces Living Labs (LLs) to enact, develop, and implement the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem on the meso-level. The LL model is also translated into guiding principles for the 'Design & Construction' of Cultural Living Labs (CLLs), within the EPIC-WE project titled Cultural Hubs. This 'Designs & Constructs' is the EPIC-WE project on the macro-level. The EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs aims to be an essential framework for fostering 'Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments' (EPIC-WE) through hosting Cultural Game Jams where young people engage and ideate cultural worlds and environments.

Throughout the development of the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs, a focus has been on creating a shared vocabulary and approach, including concept notes, visual models, and guiding principles within the project and among its QH partners. Protocol 1 emphasises the importance of cross-sector 'meetings in the middle' and interdisciplinary co-creation, which will mature and be reinforced through EPIC-WE's multiple research and innovation activities.

All in all, the D3.1 Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Innovation contributes with:

1

Establishing the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem:

The report introduces a Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Innovation Ecosystem tailored to the cultural domain. It facilitates collaboration between cultural institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth citizens to drive cultural innovation and transformation through meeting in the middle and real-world everyday practices in QH Cultural Hubs.

2

Redefining innovation with democratic, cultural, and participatory methods:

EPIC-WE emphasises democratic and participatory innovation. Iteratively applied methods such as arts-based research, citizen science, value-sensitive design, living labs, and participatory design foster open-ended cultural research and innovation.

3

Quadruple Helix: A Model for Co-creation and Democracy:

The report highlights the evolution from the traditional Triple Helix model to the Quadruple Helix, integrating civil society as a key partner. This demonstrates how cultural innovation can be co-created, democratised, user-driven, and transformative for all as well as ensuring the public plays an active role in shaping such cultural transformation.

4

Living Labs as dynamic experimental spaces:

EPIC-WE integrates Living Labs into its framework, providing real-world environments for exploring, experimenting with, evaluating, and refining its cultural innovation formats and strategies. These labs function as experimental spaces where Quadruple Helix (QH) partners collaborate on participatory, interdisciplinary, and community-driven cultural projects.

5

Developing Cultural Hubs (CHs) as Living Labs:

The report introduces Cultural Hubs as concrete and conceptual spaces for cultural research, innovation, and participation. These hubs function as Living Labs where QH partners engage in cross-sector cultural experimentation and knowledge creation.

6

Advancing Mode 3 Knowledge Creation:

EPIC-WE fosters Mode 3 knowledge, emphasising co-existence, co-evolution, and co-specialisation among the sectors' diverse knowledge paradigms. This approach accelerates cultural and social transformations beyond traditional academic and industry boundaries.

7

Promoting cross-sector collaboration 'in the middle':

The report details how QH partners collaborate through iterative, participatory processes. By creating shared ambitions, strategies, and innovation roadmaps, partners meet "in the middle" to co-create cultural innovations that no one sector or partner could achieve alone.

8

Empowering youth as active cultural innovators:

EPIC-WE's major contribution is its emphasis on youth as equal contributors and partners in cultural innovation and transformation. By involving youth as QH partners in both the ecosystem and the hub, the project strives to foster empowered cross-sector participation, imagination, creativity, and societal engagement, equipping young people with the agency and abilities to co-shape our cultural futures.

9

Iterative and reflective development of cultural innovations:

EPIC-WE adopts a participatory Design-Based Research (DBR) methodology, ensuring innovations are developed, tested, and refined through ongoing cycles of co-creation, evaluation, and adaptation within real-world cultural settings.

10

Ensuring sustainability and replicability of the EPIC-WE Model:

The report positions the EPIC-WE framework as a scalable and replicable model for cultural innovation. Other cultural institutions and QH partnerships across Europe and beyond can adapt the methodologies, tools, and principles developed.

1.4. Overview of the D3.2 Protocol 1

This report defines and explains the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs that EPIC-WE develop and apply. This is done by highlighting its theoretical foundations, potential implications, and practical applications from the D3.1 Protocol. First, Triple Helix (TH) and Quadruple Helix (QH) Innovation Ecosystems are introduced, and their key takeaways are summarised and disseminated as principles for designing the EPIC-WE framework on the macro and meso level. These principles and their implications are then put into practice to construct the design of the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem. Then, Living Labs (LL) is highlighted, drawing again on the D3.1 Protocol as an applicable way to implement the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem on the meso level. After that, key takeaways are disseminated as principles to construct and design the QH Cultural Hubs for quadruple helix partners to practice cultural innovation together ‘in the middle’ and to explore and enact their partnership through joint activities such as the EPIC-WE CGJs. Throughout the D3.2 Protocol, results and insights from the project processes and interventions are integrated to detail and extend the theoretical foundations of quadruple helix collaborations, (cultural) living labs, and QH Cultural Hubs, leading to the final and more general section of the report that synthesises overarching principles for the macro level of EPIC-WE.

Overall, D3.2, Protocol 2 provides updated results and new insights into the design and construction of Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems and QH Cultural Hubs. Principally, the D3.2 Protocol 1 on “Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation: EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs (final protocol)” expands and extends the D3.1 Protocol 1 through delivering 1) the foundational principles for the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, 2) the foundational principles for the QH Cultural Hub, 3) the sector, local, and global dimensions of these, and 4) the synthesised defining principles for the design, organisation, and running of the EPIC-WE model for Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs.

Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems

02

2. Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems

2.1 Summary of Helix Innovation Ecosystems from D3.1

The second round of DBR 'Design and Construction' of the EPIC-WE macro level innovations (2024-2025) builds directly upon the research and design foundation published in the deliverable D3.1 [Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation](#), evaluated and approved by the European Commission and Expert Evaluators during the project's periodic reporting (2024).

Helix Innovation Ecosystems are collaborative environments where multiple sectors interact to drive cross-sector innovation within a specific domain. In this context, innovation includes new knowledge, practices, products, or services. The aim is to create value through cooperative efforts, as exemplified by the EPIC-WE project, which focuses on cultural and heritage innovation through collaboration among various partners.

The Triple Helix Ecosystem (TH)

The Triple Helix (TH) model, introduced by Leydesdorff and Etzkowitz (1995), describes the increasing interdependence of industry, government, and higher education institutions (HEIs) in a knowledge-based society. This model highlights three primary roles:

The TH ecosystem operates through wealth creation, knowledge production, and normative control. However, it does not include citizens and civil society, making it insufficient for projects emphasizing democratic participation, cultural heritage, and arts-based innovation, such as EPIC-WE. Its limitations include a potential disconnect between innovation and end-user needs, leading to rejection, a lack of transparency, and superficial innovations.

The Quadruple Helix Ecosystem (QH)

The QH model builds upon TH by incorporating a fourth helix: civil society and the public. This addition emphasises the role of cultural and media-based public participation in innovation. QH involves four key partners:

Carayannis and Campbell (2006) first conceptualised the QH model, which was later refined to focus on knowledge democracy rather than merely a knowledge economy. This shift recognises that culture and media play essential roles in shaping innovation and democracy. Research has shown that the most effective QH ecosystems emphasise **public participation, cooperation between partners, and long-term commitments.**

Key aspects of the QH model include:

- **Mode 3 Knowledge Creation:** Integrates diverse knowledge paradigms to foster adaptive and interdisciplinary innovation
- **Knowledge Cultures and Democracy:** Promotes knowledge democracy, ensuring that innovations are meaningful and desired by society.
- **Diversity and Transdisciplinarity:** Encourages cross-sector knowledge exchange to drive sustainable and impactful change.

The QH ecosystem facilitates transformative cultural and social innovation by emphasising multi-directional collaboration and co-creation.

EPIC-WE as a Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem

From research and applied practices, EPIC-WE has developed guiding principles for designing and implementing a QH ecosystem tailored to culture and cultural heritage.

Key components of EPIC-WE's QH approach:

Citizens as equal partners:

Youth creators (YCs) play a central role in cultural game-making.

Democratic and participatory innovation:

Ensuring equal representation among helix partners.

Cross-sector collaboration:

Helix partners engage in macro (ecosystem-level), meso (CH-level), and micro (CGJ-level) cooperation.

Cultural and social transformation:

Innovations target game-making, European values, and cultural participation.

Domain-specific adaptation:

QH principles are modified to fit the cultural heritage and creative industries.

Knowledge co-creation:

Partners contribute expertise from their respective fields, ensuring mutual value creation.

Glocal QH Cultural Hubs:

Beyond local hubs, a meta-hub connects and disseminates cultural knowledge globally.

The QH innovation ecosystem represents a paradigm shift from traditional models by actively involving citizens and civil society. EPIC-WE serves as a case study for applying QH principles to cultural and heritage innovation.

The QH approach can lead to **sustainable, impactful innovations** that reflect and serve public interests by fostering cross-sector collaboration, participatory knowledge production, and cultural co-creation.

The continued development of EPIC-WE's QH model will refine strategies for integrating diverse partners in cultural innovation, emphasising the potential of **games and cultural heritage as tools for engagement and transformation**.

2.2 Results from EPIC-WE DBR Round 1: The Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem

Since submitting D3.1 Protocol 1 in Spring 2024, EPIC-WE has been exploring, developing, testing, and refining the concept and practice of Quadruple Helix Innovation Ecosystems within the cultural sphere, engaging diverse sector participants in co-creating innovation and research relationships. Through the first six EPIC-WE interventions carried out across three European sites in Hilversum, Aarhus, and Óbidos, the project has combined practical testing and evaluation with iterative research, design, and construction. By implementing and examining the EPIC-WE cultural innovations in action alongside qualitative research analyses of these (in local hub analyses (T4.3) and cross-hub analyses (T2.4)), this report synthesises a robust foundation of knowledge and practices for Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems.

This report incorporates thematic insights derived from diverse empirical materials, including participatory observations, reflective writing, visual ethnography, interviews, and surveys carried out as research actions in the first half of the EPIC-WE project. Additionally, it draws on feedback and feedforward sessions facilitated within the project and across collaborating sectors (T3.4). The report also includes insights from the project milestone exploring the relationship between the local and glocal (Milestone 4)—both in general and within cultural contexts—along with research publications and systematic literature reviews conducted as part of EPIC-WE, WP2.

Generally, insights from these sessions and cases highlight that each sector involved in the collaboration operates with unique goals and purposes and within different organisational and institutional rhythms, routines, and practices. Thus, it is vital to explicitly acknowledge and address these diverse priorities and conditions of work, emphasising the importance of coordination, collaboration, and communication that respects and enables diverse viewpoints and modes of participation. The key perspective here is ‘meeting in the middle’ to form ‘transformative partnerships’ that enable thinking, doing, and being otherwise. This is further connected to how the local, glocal, and sectoral dimensions are interplaying and entangled phenomena in the project that continuously affect each other in the helix partners’ collaborative and co-creative endeavours.

Figure 1: Interplays between Sectors, Local, and Glocal

During the first round of DBR interventions, it was also discussed that the participatory focus should extend beyond simply delivering cultural games or cultural game jams to end-users and towards fostering more interdependent, meaningful, and inclusive cultural collaborations across sectors and with youth as key partners. This emphasised the value of building and sustaining cross-sector partnerships between cultural organisations, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth that reflect shared understanding and mutual respect.

The project – while not explicitly addressing this but highlighted as insights by different participating sectors – relates to principles of pragmatism, which emphasise practical experiences and knowledge, focusing on experiential learning, integrating theory and practice, and scaffolding reflections during and after practice. It underscores the importance of learning through experience, within and across sectors, where real-world situations and practical problem-solving are central to learning and development. In EPIC-WE, it relates to the feedback loops and iterations between theoretical understandings and practical experiments of the quadruple helix innovation ecosystem in a cultural context and the overarching methodology of design-based research and innovation connected to pragmatism.

Overall, insights and results highlight the multifaceted nature of building and sustaining quadruple helix innovation ecosystems within the cultural sphere through results and insights from the project's preliminary research and innovation parts. EPIC-WE demonstrates the value of fostering inclusive, interdependent, and meaningful collaborations across diverse sectors by integrating theoretical insights with practical experimentation. The project accentuates the importance of addressing differing realities, priorities, and practices through coordinated and co-creative efforts that emphasise communication and mutual respect. EPIC-WE advances cultural innovation through its iterative and pragmatic approach and sets a foundation for future explorations of collaborative, value-driven frameworks in cultural and creative contexts. In the following paragraphs, the report presents the developed foundational principles for constructing and implementing Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems, along with detailing the sectoral, local, and glocal dimensions of such systems, drawing on tangible insights, processes, developments, and experiences from the project.

2.3 Foundational Principles for Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem

From the mentioned EPIC-WE research and innovation activities, DBR interventions, and the resulting deliverables, reports and research publications, 10 foundational principles for developing, implementing, and operating Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems can be presented. These have further been integrated with the insights from sector, local, and glocal dimensions described above to ensure that the ecosystem – and its principles – are emerging from thorough research grounding and its application in practice within the three QH Cultural Hubs for the duration of the project.

Foundational Principles for Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems

1

Co-creation and inclusive innovation

The QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem fosters co-creation by integrating perspectives from creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, higher education institutions, and youth citizens.

These four sectors collaborate across local European QH Cultural Hubs – in EPIC-WE, it is Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum – ensuring that cultural innovation and transformation are both contextually relevant and glocally informed.

This participatory model strengthens legitimacy and acceptance, leading to more sustainable innovations that bridge local and global cultural influences.

To maximise impact, co-creation should be embedded in all phases of development, from ideation to implementation, ensuring cultural heritage remains a living, evolving part of society.

2

Interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration

The QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem is cultivated through breaking silos between sectors, promoting interdisciplinary transformative partnerships that leverage diverse knowledges and expertise to address complex cultural innovation and societal challenges.

Within EPIC-WE, cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth meet in the middle to engage in cultural innovation and transformation. By engaging local hubs across different European regions, partnerships remain deeply rooted in their specific cultural contexts while benefiting from global insights.

Cross-sectoral collaboration ensures that innovation processes are adaptable and inclusive, incorporating diverse perspectives across disciplines and sectors. Such cross-sector partnerships sustain meaningful engagement, fostering cultural empowerment and societal impact.

3

Sustainability and empowered participation

Innovations within the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem should prioritise empowered participation.

By leveraging cross-sectoral partnerships, EPIC-WE's ecosystem fosters resilience and value creation that extends beyond local interventions to glocal applications.

The project partners' everyday practice of QH QH Cultural Hubs and co-creating Cultural Game Jams exemplify this by revitalising cultural heritage through committed, participatory, and co-empowering cultural action and innovations. Integrating sustainability considerations means balancing short-term gains with long-term cultural benefits for both local communities and glocal networks.

4

Open knowledge sharing and transparency

A thriving QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem relies on open knowledge creation and exchange among sectors, partners, participants and wider communities.

Focusing on open innovation, transparent processes, public goods and freely shared resources and results enhances mutual learning and accelerates cross-sector innovation capabilities.

EPIC-WE fosters open dialogue and the sharing of resources and results through open research, the creation of freely available online resources, policy roundtables, and publicly open cross-sectoral capacity building, strengthening the exchange of specialised knowledge beyond local boundaries.

Ensuring equitable and democratic access to both research and innovations empowers all actors within the QH ecosystem, making cultural heritage and innovation more accessible, sustainable, valuable, and participatory.

5

Mutual trust and shared values in innovation

Building strong QH collaborations requires trust, commitment, and negotiated meaning and values among partners.

In EPIC-WE, QH Cultural Hubs function as sites for meeting in the middle to co-create and where mutual respect and shared goals drive engagement between creative industries, cultural institutions, higher education institutions, and youth.

Trust is cultivated through committed partnerships, mutual care, consistent engagement, and participatory decision-making processes.

6

Curious, creative, and collective practices

The QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem embraces exploration, experimentation, risk-taking, and an imaginative mindset to drive transformative innovations in culture and cultural heritage.

EPIC-WE fosters transformative partnerships where all QH partners work together in real-world, real-life, everyday innovation by continuously meeting in the middle and across QH Cultural Hubs.

Supporting the development, implementation, and operation of such ecosystems strengthens cultural heritage and empowers cross-sector participation and innovation as well as local-glocal cultural ecosystems.

7

Knowledge hybridity through partnerships across domains and sectors

The EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem is not a structure for knowledge transfer but a space for the formation of new, hybrid knowledges through committed and co-creative partnerships across domains.

Each helix partner- whether from CIs, CHIs, HEIs, or YCs – brings not only expertise but also distinct modes of knowledge-making reconfiguring roles, methods, and practices in the co-owned middle of cultural innovation.

In EPIC-WE, QH Cultural Hubs become sites of transformative partnerships, where research, innovation, and concrete practices are continuously negotiated, contested, and reshaped through cross-sectoral and transdisciplinary engagement.

8

Generative friction as a driver of epistemic and cultural transformation

The EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem thrives not in seamless consensus but in generative friction - the productive tensions that emerge when diverse partners, disciplines, and sectors meet in the middle.

Generative friction is not an obstacle to cultural innovation; it is the very condition that makes innovation possible.

The meeting of different values and logics—those of research, industry, culture, and youth citizenship—demands both resilience and openness to other ways of knowing, being, and doing.

9

Evaluation and culture-based decision-making

Assessing the impact of QH initiatives is crucial for continuous improvement, particularly in cross-sector and cross-disciplinary collaborations.

EPIC-WE integrates qualitative evaluation frameworks native to and suited for the domains of culture, cultural heritage, and the humanities.

Transparent and open reporting on and sharing of all research and innovation outcomes fosters trust and engagement from all actors, reinforcing the ecosystem's collaborative and participatory nature.

2.4 Sector dimensions

The EPIC-WE quadruple helix cultural innovation ecosystem for research and innovation is anchored in four distinct sectors—cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth representing civil society. These sectors are enacted across three local European QH Cultural Hubs in Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum, each integrating all four sectors. As such, the EPIC-WE consortium operates as a collaborative partner network designed to foster transformative partnerships in research and innovation, with these partnerships manifested across countries, sites, and sectors, both locally and glocally.

EPIC-WE thus gathers four stakeholders as partners in its Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem: creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and youth citizens. One of the strengths of the Quadruple Helix Innovation Ecosystem is its approach towards bringing together specialised experts and professionals from each sector, creating a collaborative environment that leverages diverse knowledge and expertise. In the context of the EPIC-WE, each helix partner is a professional or academic network or media partner within their own specific domain.

The four sectors collaborate in and develop interwoven partnerships, creating more equitable and inclusive cross-sector cultural collaboration and innovation. The EPIC-WE project consortium itself functions as a Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, bringing together leaders and practitioners from research, culture, and creative sectors and inviting YCs as a fourth helix partner. By engaging youth citizens in cultural game-making practices during cultural game jams, they work alongside the other three helix partners in each of the three QH Cultural Hubs, and by co-designing events, activities, and processes while representing themselves as youth citizens, they become integral parts of the cultural quadruple helix approach.

The EPIC-WE project thus focuses on developing cultural innovation ecosystems, knowledge cultures, and collaboration models, as detailed in protocol D3.1, to facilitate such cross-sector cultural partnerships. These partnerships are experimental, both epistemic and practical (D3.1, pp. 19-20); in other words, they are about problematising, creating, doing, and reflecting together. The EPIC-WE QH partners are committed to building a cultural innovation ecosystem that prioritises cooperation, democratic and equal partnerships, and exchanging knowledge and cultural practices, as scholars like von Hippel (2006) and DiSalvo (2022) emphasise. This involves designing a multi-level framework of a QH macro-perspective, a materialisation of it as a meso-level, and its products and interventions on a micro-level.

From a Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem perspective, the vital aims are to establish and sustain supportive, collaborative partnerships, thus also working towards integrating and empowering youth to become active participants and co-shapers of the ecosystem as the fourth and public helix. It means taking youth perspectives seriously in formal project contexts as equal partners in QH collaborations and hub configurations.

In EPIC-WE, Youth Advisory Boards have been assembled by recruiting diverse participants from the cultural game jams. This ensures that the Youth Advisory Boards continuously grow throughout the project's lifetime with the hosted cultural game jams. It also ensures that the youths becoming collaborative partners have unique lived experiences from participating in the project's interventions, providing perspectives and reflections of vital importance. In the collaborative partnership, the youth citizens enact the fourth sector of the ecosystem as equal partners, becoming more than end-users and partners in the processes of exploration, research, and innovation (D3.1, pp. 34-35).

2.5 Local dimensions

EPIC-WE develop processes and practices to create a quadruple-helix cultural innovation ecosystem that facilitates close collaboration between local (and beyond) creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, higher education institutions, and youth citizens. This ecosystem seeks to co-shape new cultural futures, reimagine European values and culture, innovate cultural products through cultural game jams, and revitalise cultural heritage as public goods.

The EPIC-WE cultural QH approach is implemented across three European sites—Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos—each bringing together the four key stakeholders. However, the institutions and organisations involved are not identical across sites. The higher education institutions are the most similar, while the creative industries and cultural heritage institutions are more diverse. For instance, in Óbidos, the creative industry partner is a game development company, while in Hilversum, it specialises in interactive art and media, and in Aarhus, an umbrella organisation incubates emerging game companies. The cultural partners also vary: in Denmark, it is a historical art museum; in Hilversum, a digital and historical media archive; and in Óbidos, the municipality. While the configuration of the QH adapts to the local needs, context, and opportunities, it remains grounded within the theoretical framework of cultural innovation ecosystems.

2.6 Glocal dimensions

Drawing from the project milestone report (Milestone 4) on the interplay of local and glocal, we argue that "glocal culture" captures the dynamic interplay between global influences and local cultural practices, emphasising the mutual adaptation and blending of these elements to create unique cultural forms (Kjeldgaard & Askegaard, 2006; Mihr, 2022; Popov et al., 2019). This glocal perspective challenges the traditional binary opposition of global and local, presenting them as entangled and mutually constitutive (Roudometof, 2015). Glocalisation, as an emerging framework, goes beyond the linearity of internationalisation by fostering reflexive exchanges of global and local knowledge (Patel & Lynch, 2013). This is particularly relevant in youth culture and thus to EPIC-WE, where global styles inspire localised adaptations through processes of appropriation, reflecting the continuous interactions of globalisation and localisation (Kjeldgaard & Askegaard, 2005). By shifting from cultural awareness to intercultural awareness, glocal approaches address contemporary mobility and cultural diversity, fostering identities simultaneously rooted in the local and enriched by the global (Guilherme, 2020).

In research and practice, glocalisation redefines spatial boundaries, portraying the local as a socially constructed and fluid concept shaped by global flows rather than a fixed geographical point (Roudometof, 2015). This understanding encourages a shift from viewing space and place as oppositional to recognising their co-creative potential. Glocal perspectives and practices support the creation of new social spaces that reconcile tensions between the global and local, fostering cultural exchanges that respect both uniqueness and interconnectedness. It also highlights the role of glocalisation in addressing global challenges, viewing it as a process of norm and cultural diffusion between the local and global (Mihir, 2022).

While still developing, EPIC-WE's transnational and cross-cultural collaborations across the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem exemplify glocal approaches and perspectives. Here, local partnerships are inspired and imbued by other partnerships and configurations, and vice versa; the glocal configuration of the QH in EPIC-WE is supported and strengthened. Tangibly, the project performs, e.g., approaches towards policy roundtables, cross-sectoral roundtables and workshops, research analyses within glocal networks, collaborative networks within and beyond the local QH configurations, and continuously includes professional network, media and dissemination partners to enable the strengths in combining, sharing and utilising specialised knowledge and practices beyond and through local endeavours.

Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs

03

3. Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs in EPIC-WE serve as dynamic living labs adapted to the domain of culture and cultural heritage. Within the EPIC-WE project, they are established, run, and evaluated across three European sites: Óbidos (Portugal), Hilversum (The Netherlands), and Aarhus (Denmark). Drawing on the EPIC-WE cultural adaptation of the Quadruple Helix Innovation Ecosystem, these QH Cultural Hubs are practised through the coming together of four key sectors: higher education institutions, cultural heritage institutions, creative industry, and youth citizens. They foster cross-sector, transdisciplinary collaborations through ‘meeting in the middle’, aiming to empower all partners to co-create meaningful, value-sensitive cultural innovations. The QH Cultural Hubs embody theoretical-practical innovation and cultural experimentation by translating abstract ecosystems and models into concrete, localised practices for cultural research and innovation. Guided by dedicated hub leads, QH Cultural Hubs facilitate democratic dialogue, cultural co-creation, and empowered participation - ensuring all sectors – including youth – evolve from consultation to equal partnership. Over the first two years, continuous development, testing, and iterative refinement have developed and strengthened the real-world practice of the QH Cultural Hubs, where partners collaboratively preserve, reimagine, and innovate cultural heritage through game-making as culture-making, ensuring lasting cultural value, impact, and support for European cultural policy objectives.

3.1 Summary of Living Labs and QH Cultural Hubs from D3.1

The second round of DBR ‘Design and Construction’ of the EPIC-WE macro level innovations (2024-2025) builds directly upon the research and design foundation published in the deliverable D3.1 [Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation](#), evaluated and approved by the European Commission and Expert Evaluators during the project’s periodic reporting (2024).

Here, Living Labs (LLs) are an underlying model for the QH Cultural Hubs, where participatory and democratic cultural innovation is practised through real-world everyday action. Originating from MIT’s PlaceLab in 2004, LLs emphasise end-user participation, focusing on cultural values rather than technical solutions. They integrate methods from participatory design, democratic innovation, and human-centred research to create concrete and practical open innovation labs that materialise the QH innovation ecosystem and foster co-creation, rapid prototyping, and iterative testing within a real-life environment practised through all QH partners meeting to collaborate in the middle. As such, LLs shift research and innovation from technology-driven solutions to democratic participation and citizen co-creation.

Key characteristics of LLs include:

- Real-world settings for research and innovation.
- Cross-sector collaboration.
- End-user participation and co-creation.
- Multi-disciplinary teams engaging in workshops, interventions, and experiments.

Different types of LLs

Research-driven LLs

Focused on knowledge creation

Industry-driven LLs

Used by companies for product and service innovation.

Community-driven LLs

Developed for social change and democratic design.

Testbed-driven LLs

Used to test and demonstrate innovations in real-life settings.

Most LLs combine aspects of these categories to suit specific contexts and objectives.

Cultural Living Labs (CLLs)

Cultural Living Labs (CLLs) adapt the LL framework to focus on cultural innovation. They create environments for engaging in cultural research and innovation within Quadruple Helix (QH) ecosystems.

Unlike traditional LLs, CLLs:

- Centre on cultural value, experiences, and participation.
- Foster cross-sector partnerships in cultural heritage, media, and the arts.
- Develop innovation organically through co-creation among QH partners.
- Serve as platforms for new cultural formats, products, and participatory processes.

CLLs position research partners as both innovators and creators, merging diverse expertise to shape cultural futures. They emphasise de-centring existing knowledge structures and centring new collaborative modes of cultural innovation.

Guiding principles for CLLs in cultural research and innovation:

- **CLLs as QH enablers**
Transform theoretical QH ecosystems into tangible practice.
- **Cultural meeting places**
Foster democratic, participatory, and collective ownership.
- **Knowledge creators**
Generate cultural knowledge through real-world engagement.
- **Living cultures**
Integrate into cultural heritage sites, museums, and public spaces.
- **Tailored typologies**
Adapt to specific research, innovation, or community-driven objectives.
- **Empowered participation**
Encourage bottom-up innovation and inclusive cultural transformation.

EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs

EPIC-WE connects LLs and CLLs with its QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem. These QH Cultural Hubs:

- Involve HEIs, CHIs, CIs, and YC (youth) as researchers, innovators, and culture-makers.
- Focus on cultural heritage, game-making as culture-making, and empowered participation.
- Develop innovative formats for games through and for cultural engagement.
- Serve as dynamic cultural environments for iterative collaboration and experimentation.

Structure and Impact of EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hubs

Different levels of engagement:

Local: Site-specific CHs – in EPIC-WE: Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos.

Glocal: Cross-hub collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Global: Ecosystems, models, and methodologies for broader application.

Different sectors involved:

Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs):

Provide knowledge, materials, and environments.

Creative Industries (CIs):

Offer expertise in game design and digital media.

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs):

Supply research methodologies and theoretical grounding.

Youth Citizens (YCs):

Contribute cultural perspectives and innovative participation.

EPIC-WE's CHs and CLLs create environments for cultural innovation, research, and transformation. By integrating diverse sectors, disciplines, and methodologies, they foster partnership innovation in cultural heritage.

3.2 Results from EPIC-WE DBR Round 1: The QH Cultural Hub

With this report, the EPIC-WE approach towards Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs is detailed and discussed as a new cross-sector partnership format and approach towards cultural co-creation and innovation. Generally, QH Cultural Hubs serve as sites for participatory co-creation, fostering dynamic collaboration among diverse partners, participants, and stakeholders. Grounded in the Living Lab framework (as defined and described in detail in D3.1, [Protocol 1: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation](#)), such hubs enable iterative, inclusive processes where all participants are active partners, inviting and empowering participants to shape and reimagine cultural futures. Activities and interventions like cultural game jams exemplify this approach by providing hands-on, participatory formats for engaging cultural innovation in concrete cultural spaces (D3.1, [Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit](#)).

As earlier described, the project and the QH Cultural Hubs involve four helix partners: Cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) play a crucial role by providing locations, cultural heritage, and cultural knowledge, which serve as the foundation for creating games through and for culture. Creative industries (CIs) contribute with game-making tools, game jam practices, and expertise in game design, enabling the production of game jams and games that engage directly with and transform cultural heritage. Higher education institutions (HEIs) offer cutting-edge methodologies and the best research and educational practices to ensure the QH Cultural Hubs and Cultural Game Jams have a solid research foundation and well-argued design and practice. Youth participants bring valuable voices and transformative practices by actively exploring and innovating games and culture by acting as culture-makers and game-makers.

QH Cultural Hubs reconfigure traditional boundaries, encouraging transversal collaboration across sectors, disciplines, and cultural contexts, allowing for the dynamic reconfiguration of roles, hierarchies, values, and practices. By navigating fuzzy boundaries—such as between the local and global, tangible and intangible, or natural and cultural heritage—QH Cultural Hubs enable open and experimental collaborations that embrace the complexities of different sector, partner, participant, and stakeholder goals, values, methods, and practices, which has been a core reflection point in the ongoing evaluations of the three QH Cultural Hubs in the project (Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos QH Cultural Hubs).

The QH Cultural Hub model operates at various local levels to partake in culture-making and facilitate innovation in and through cultural heritage. At the local level, activities focus on three key hubs: Aarhus in Denmark, Hilversum in the Netherlands, and Óbidos in Portugal. The three QH Cultural Hubs are interconnected through a glocal cross-hub approach that emphasises exchanges and connections between them (as outlined in Milestone 4), creating a networked model for co-operation, collaboration and co-creative practices. Through this, the EPIC-WE project offers a scalable QH Ecosystem at the local level, including a QH Cultural Hub model and Cultural Game Jam Kit that has been iteratively developed, implemented, tested, researched, and evaluated to be disseminated to the involved sectors throughout EU at the end of the project (2026).

3.3. Foundational Principles for Cultural Hubs

1

Democratise cultural innovation through including citizens and users as core partners in the QH Cultural Hub

In the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, citizens/users are central partners in cultural research and innovation. As equal partners and active co-creators within the QH Cultural Hub and in its execution of cultural events such as Cultural Game Jams, citizens/users engage in research and innovation on an equal footing with the other helix partners. Equal participation among cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions and citizens/users ensures that cultural transformation and innovation remain democratic, authentic, credible, and impactful. The QH Cultural Hub model fosters democratic and participatory co-creation by embedding citizens/users at every phase, enabling them to participate meaningfully in research and innovation activities as a deliberate form of culture-making

QH Cultural Hubs function as collaborative spaces where Youth Citizens (YCs) are not merely observers but central actors in cultural research and innovation. Including YCs in the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem ensures that cultural production remains participatory, relevant, and reflective of contemporary societal shifts. Through Cultural Game Jams (CGJs), YCs actively shape cultural narratives by engaging in game-making as a means of culture-making. This participatory model fosters cultural innovations' credibility, authenticity, and long-term viability by directly involving those who consume and shape culture.

Beyond game-making, YCs participate in decision-making structures, ensuring their voices influence cultural policies and practices. Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), Creative Industries (CIs), and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) work alongside YCs as equal partners, contributing to the co-creation of innovative cultural experiences.

The equal representation within EPIC-WE structures, including its Executive Board and project collaborations, guarantees that co-creation extends beyond mere consultation to full participatory inclusion.

This approach is reinforced through Design-Based Research (DBR), ensuring that iterative development aligns with all stakeholders' real needs and aspirations. The practice of inclusion transforms CHs into dynamic cultural ecosystems where citizens become active contributors to cultural knowledge production, expanding the potential of cultural heritage beyond institutional boundaries.

2

Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation

QH Cultural Hubs are deliberately designed as diverse and inclusive environments where cross-sector collaboration and co-creation thrive. They are formed on the premise of each sector being an equal partner in cultural research and innovation and that each partner is open to being transformed by the others to ‘think, do and be otherwise’ by going beyond sectorial boundaries and methods. Each partner must be open to reciprocal transformation through the mutual integration of ‘alien’ knowledges, values, meanings, and discourses.

Transformative partnerships in QH Cultural Hubs dissolve traditional boundaries between sectors, disciplines, and institutions. These partnerships do not simply facilitate cultural innovation but fundamentally reshape how collaboration occurs. The principle of ‘meeting in the middle’ guides this transformation, ensuring that different knowledge domains, whether from academia, industry, cultural institutions, or the public, merge to create new cultural possibilities. HEIs, in particular, must embrace their role as enablers rather than gatekeepers of knowledge, welcoming external perspectives and allowing reciprocal transformation between sectors.

Through Cultural Hubs, knowledge is not transferred but co-produced equitably, acknowledging the value of each partner’s expertise and lived experience. CHIs contribute historical and cultural depth, CIs bring creative and technological skills, HEIs provide research methodologies, and YCs offer contemporary insights into emerging cultural practices. These roles’ continuous adaptation and problematisation ensure that QH Cultural Hubs remain dynamic, responsive, and forward-thinking.

By fostering sustained collaboration, QH Cultural Hubs create ‘epic we’ partnerships –mutually beneficial, non-competitive, and deeply interwoven stakeholder relationships. These partnerships are built on trust, shared responsibilities, and a commitment to long-term cultural and civic innovation. Forming such partnerships requires a shift in institutional mindsets, embracing non-hierarchical models of governance and co-creation. As a result, QH Cultural Hubs evolve into engines of cultural transformation, where the traditional distinctions between research, practice, and public engagement are continuously redefined.

3

Institutes meeting in the middle

QH Cultural Hubs deliberately institute and become materialised by ‘meeting in the middle.’ They function as the operational space for cross-sector transformative partnerships. These meetings in the middle require all partners to ‘meet each other halfway’ in terms of vocabularies, ideas, methodologies, practices, and expectations. QH Cultural Hubs enacted through ‘meetings in the middle’ foster continued dynamic negotiation, enabling the reimagination and reconfiguration of cultural practices. This, in turn, demands resilience and commitment from all sector partners as it destabilises the stable and stabilises the unstable to generate new forms of cultural collaboration that transcend traditional sectorial divides.

The core philosophy of QH Cultural Hubs is the practice of ‘meeting in the middle.’ This principle acknowledges that meaningful cultural collaboration requires negotiation, flexibility, and the willingness to engage with unfamiliar perspectives. CHs act as spaces where disciplines, traditions, and methodologies intersect, generating new ways of thinking and doing culture. Meeting in the middle is not about compromising one’s position but creating shared spaces where differences become productive. The process of co-creation thrives in these dynamic exchanges, allowing cultural practices to be continuously reimaged and revitalised. This principle requires partners to be comfortable with epistemic discomfort—accepting that cultural innovation often emerges from challenging, conflictual, or unfamiliar interactions.

By committing to this practice, CHs ensure that cultural innovation remains authentic and reflective of multiple societal narratives. The work within these hubs is iterative, requiring sustained engagement and reflection. Stabilising and destabilising cultural norms is an ongoing process wherein co-creation becomes a continuous negotiation of meaning, values, and creative expression.

4

Practice co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for public good(s)

Innovation in QH Cultural Hubs is experimental, iterative, open-ended, and focused on co-creating cultural public good(s). By prioritising co-creation for public good(s) over purely technical, economical, or instrumental solutions, QH Cultural Hubs ensure that cultural goods and innovations remain valuable, meaningful, and freely accessible for all. As public goods, cultural innovation must serve the public good, positioning cultural QH Cultural Hubs and cultural game jams as drivers for democratic and empowered participation in culture.

QH Cultural Hubs foreground co-creation as the primary mode of cultural innovation, ensuring that new cultural products and experiences emerge from collective engagement rather than isolated institutional agendas. These hubs integrate participatory design, democratic methodologies, and transdisciplinary collaboration to create cultural solutions that serve broader societal needs. Innovation in CHs is not limited to technological advancements but includes new cultural formats, modes of expression, and participatory experiences. Employing methods such as arts-based research, speculative design, and iterative experimentation, CHs facilitate cultural production that remains open-ended, evolving alongside community interactions. Rather than treating citizens as passive recipients of culture, CHs position them as active agents in defining culture and how it is represented.

By embedding cultural innovation in democratic participation, CHs cultivate sustainable cultural ecosystems. They ensure that cultural products—whether games, exhibitions, or performances—reflect historical heritage and continuously evolve through contemporary engagement. This principle positions cultural transformation as a public good, aligning CH activities with broader civic and democratic values. As a result, QH Cultural Hubs serve as both incubators and accelerators of cultural knowledge, sustaining long-term creative and participatory momentum.

5

Develop real-world, real-life Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs are established and operate within larger existing (global-glocal-local) cultural ecosystems. As such, QH Cultural Hubs are naturally part of and take part in the everyday real-life of real-world spaces such as museums, libraries, cultural centres, public spaces, and heritage sites. Rather than erecting external ‘innovation spaces’, QH Cultural Hub partners use their ‘cultural homes’ to practice co-design transformation in collaboration with local citizens, users, and stakeholders. This requires that these spaces be reconfigured to be collectively occupied and acted on by the QH Cultural Hub partners, transforming and de-centring traditional institutional frameworks and spaces to allow new modes of living, acting, and being together within a shared, participatory environment.

QH Cultural Hubs are deeply embedded in real-world contexts, ensuring cultural research and innovation occur within lived environments rather than isolated institutional settings. These hubs are housed within museums, cultural centres, public spaces, and heritage sites, directly interacting with communities and local ecosystems. Integrating QH Cultural Hubs within everyday cultural life enables direct engagement with local stakeholders, ensuring that innovation is contextually relevant and responsive. Rather than imposing top-down frameworks, QH Cultural Hubs are platforms for co-designing cultural interventions alongside those who live and experience them. This participatory model strengthens the sustainability of cultural innovation, as transformations are rooted in genuine community needs. The principle of real-world engagement reinforces culture’s role as a participatory and evolving practice by positioning QH Cultural Hubs as active spaces for lived culture. It encourages the development of spaces that accommodate experimental, interdisciplinary, and community-driven approaches to cultural creation and heritage preservation.

6

Advance empowered participation in culture

QH Cultural Hubs must strive to foster inclusive, diverse, and equitable participation, ensuring that all helix partners feel they are co-owners of the QH Cultural Hub space and operations and equally invited to take part in the cultural innovation decisions, activities, practices and experiences happening there. Empowered participation extends beyond being listened to or being consulted, positioning every participant as a core partner and indispensable member. QH Cultural Hubs must prioritise cultural innovation created through co-operation and co-creation and initiated from experiences of cultural imagination, agency, belonging, and respect. Success is measured by the QH Cultural Hub's ability to create a space for empowered participation among its partners and its users, fostering new and potentially more empowering ways of engaging with and co-creating cultural heritage, spaces, experiences, and futures.

Empowerment within QH Cultural Hubs extends beyond participation—it ensures that all stakeholders hold meaningful influence over cultural research and innovation. CHs foster shared agency, mutual respect, and a commitment to inclusivity, ensuring that cultural transformation is co-owned by all participants. This principle places equal importance on empowering CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and YCs, recognising that each helix partner contributes uniquely to the innovation ecosystem. Cultural participation is not limited to passive engagement but requires active involvement in decision-making, cultural production, and governance. QH Cultural Hubs flourish when their participants feel valued, respected, and equipped to shape cultural narratives in significant ways.

EPIC-WE embodies this vision, positioning empowered participation as the foundation of its cultural and civic innovation strategy. QH Cultural Hub's success is measured not solely by outputs but by the extent to which they nurture civic imagination, collective creativity, and the capacity for individuals to meaningfully contribute to cultural futures. By championing this approach, QH Cultural Hubs redefines cultural participation as an inclusive, dynamic, and transformative practice.

3.4 Sector Dimensions

In the QH Cultural Hubs, each sector and sector partner provide unique and specific expertise and ways of knowing to strengthen the joint knowledge production, the shared innovation aims and outcomes, and the boundary-crossing and collaborative explorations, problematisations, interventions, and reflections.

Each helix within the EPIC-WE QH ecosystem contributes indispensable domain-specific expertise in the QH Cultural Hubs:

- **Cultural Heritage Institutions:** Offer knowledge of cultural heritage, storytelling, art, exhibitions, and audience engagement.
- **Creative Industries:** Provide expertise in game design, programming, game-making tools, participatory practices like game jams, and expert knowledge of gaming worlds and environments.
- **Higher Education Institutions:** Provide substantiated frameworks for democratic and participatory design, value-sensitive methodologies, and arts- and humanities-based approaches.
- **Youth Citizens:** Contribute perspectives on youth cultures, engagement, empowerment, and the cultural value of games and heritage for young people – through integration as partners in the QH Cultural Hubs and within Youth Advisory Boards in EPIC-WE.

This cross-sector collaboration thrives on these domains' coexistence, co-evolution, and co-specialization. It ensures that each helix partner's unique insights and skills enrich all phases of the innovation process—from ideation to implementation. Including media, networking, and dissemination professionals further enhances the ecosystem's capacity to create impactful and widely disseminated cultural innovations. By intentionally blurring distinctions between research, practice, and innovation, these hubs serve as spaces for epistemic partnerships, where each helix's expertise converges to co-create knowledge and cultural products. This approach recognises that cultural innovation is an emergent process, reflecting the dynamic interplay of local life, sectoral roles, and collaborative practices.

The EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hub approach recognises the need to enhance its outreach, dissemination, and cross-sectoral impact by integrating professional networking, media, and communication expertise. While helix partners bring domain-specific strengths—for example, higher education institutions excel in research methodologies, academic networking, publications, and dissemination—exploitation and media communication are not their primary specialisations. To address this, EPIC-WE established a glocal QH Cultural Hub to complement and connect its three local QH Cultural Hubs in Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos. This glocal hub is conceptualised as a sort of meta-hub, connecting local partners and their actions and activities with global strategies, policies, and networks. By embedding this expertise, the glocal QH Cultural Hub ensures that EPIC-WE's research, innovations and insights are effectively communicated and disseminated across the QH Cultural Hubs and tailored to their QH sectors, partners, and participants, as well as amplifying external stakeholder knowledge and engagement.

3.5 Local Dimensions

As described, EPIC-WE collaboration by and through QH Cultural Hubs extends across five countries and three hubs. QH Cultural Hub partners in Denmark include ARoS (AROS), Filmby Aarhus (AAKS), and Aarhus University (AU). The Hilversum QH Cultural Hub comprises The Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV), DROPSTUFF MEDIA (DM), and Hogeschool van Amsterdam (HVA/AUAS), while the Óbidos QH Cultural Hub includes Universidade Lusófona (LU), BATTLESHEEP (BS), and Óbidos Municipal Council (CMO). In the project, MEET (Italy) represents a glocal media and culture partner, while KEA (Belgium) ensures glocal and global communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project results and activities. Finally, CBC serves as glocal creative industry partner working with establishing glocal and global policies and capacity building. Together, these partners meet in the middle to research and innovate across cultural heritage, creative industries, and higher education sectors while including and empowering youth as epistemic and practical partners in the QH Cultural Hubs.

A QH Cultural Hub is formed by the QH actors, with a named hub leader responsible for its coordination, communication, and development. Each QH Cultural Hub configures its rhythms and routines differently. However, it is manifested through continuous co-creative digital and analogue meetings while becoming in vivo labs through everyday practices and real-world joint experimentation and interventions. Each hub works in a specific cultural, societal, and local context. As such, it is more meaningful to highlight the defining elements that cut across the operationalisation of the three QH Cultural Hubs in the EPIC-WE project:

- 1. Co-creative and co-operative.** Co-creative approaches – to exploration and design – and co-operative (i.e., mutual and shared) ownership of the QH Cultural Hub.
- 2. Experimental partnerships.** Joint problematisations of the cultural and societal world through epistemic and practical partnerships and relationships.
- 3. Transversal collaborations.** Non-dichotomous, non-binary, transdisciplinary, caring and relational partnerships form the inner workings of the QH Cultural Hub.
- 4. Local structure; glocal connections.** The QH Cultural Hub has a hub leader whose role is that of a coordinating co-partner, enabling communicative and collaborative clarity – within the hub, across the hubs, and hence as both local and glocal entities.
- 5. Developed and driven as cultural living labs.** Participant-centred research and innovation models, multi-method approaches, and context-sensitive activities and inquiry form the foundation of the QH Cultural Hubs.

3.6 Glocal Dimensions

The glocal dimensions and workings of QH Cultural Hubs are continuously discussed and evaluated in the project through cross-hub meetings, glocal approaches to CGJs, shared communication and dissemination efforts (such as the cross-sectoral cross-hub EPIC-WE research group), and the shared CGJ Kit and EPIC-WE Protocols 1-4 approach to interventions with shared glocal processes, methods, themes, protocols, and cross-hub Youth Advisory Boards.

According to the D2.2 State of the Art in game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens, glocal exchanges in the EPIC-WE project highlight the partners' cultural impact. "Culture" refers to the distinct cultures of higher education institutions, creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, youth citizens, and the broader cultural identity of a European region. In glocal cross-hub meetings (T4.1), the three QH Cultural Hubs have emphasised that the "glocal" concept captures the dynamic relationship between global and local contexts. It highlights how global ideas, strategies, processes, materials, research, and innovations are integrated and adapted within local environments. This approach addresses global challenges through localised partnership actions and vice versa, enabling local cultures, methods, and values to be respected and incorporated. The concept of the 'glocal' aligns with thinking globally and acting locally (Coker, 2014), promoting cross-border and transnational collaboration by tailoring global problems and perspectives to meet local ambitions and contexts. In this sense, the glocal approach fosters flexibility and adaptation, where local cultures influence global narratives and vice versa, reinforcing interconnectedness and glocal innovation of cultural heritage and youth empowerment.

The QH Cultural Hubs cross-hub collaboration (T4.1; T3.4) furthermore show that glocal Cultural Game Jams can provide significant value by deepening the understanding of how local perspectives intersect with global issues while functioning as a site for cultural heritage research and innovation in action. These CGJ events lead to innovative cross-sector outcomes that address local and global challenges while creating opportunities for cultural exchange and cross-hub connectedness. Supporting the exchange of ideas between the QH Cultural Hubs under this glocal model can enhance local innovations' overall impact and sustainability.

CREATING THE EPIC WE

04

4. Creating the EPIC-WE

4.1 The EPIC-WE model for QH Cultural Hubs

QH Cultural Hubs

1 Requirement 1: Include citizens as equal partners

In the development of the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, citizens play a central and critical role.

In the QH:

- **citizens are positioned as valued co-inventors** of their desired cultural products and futures
- **citizens are included as central research and innovation helix partner** to enhance the credibility, authenticity, cultural value, and benefits of its research & innovations

2 Requirement 2 Innovation through democratic & participatory processes

Formation of the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem is distinctly visible in the configuration of equal rights, roles, and responsibilities. In the QH:

- There is an **equal distribution** of helix partners from CIs, CHIs, and HEIs with equal representation and rights.

QH CULTURAL HUBS

1 Requirement 1: Initiate Living Labs as QH transformer

QH Cultural Hubs are based on Living Labs principles. They transform the QH ecosystem into 'everyday practices' by bringing together diverse partners in culture and engaging them in real-world on the ground practices.

The goal of the QH Cultural Hub is to **form an 'epic we'** that can carry out QH research and innovation:

- First, by facilitating a **'de-centring'** of pre-existing sector-confined ways of knowing, doing and being.
- Second, by enabling a **'centring'** of new modes of collective and co-creative knowing, doing and being by a meeting in the middle and thinking 'other-wise' within the QH Cultural Hub

2 Requirement 2: Set up Living Labs as cultural meeting places

- Cultural Hubs are conducive cultural environments and meeting places characterised by 'communal ownership' through co-operative operations & democratic participation
- For this to happen, QH partners must be ready to 'meet each other halfway' and leave behind preconceptions and taken-for-granted knowledges, methods, and practices.

- each partner is to be acknowledged and involved as **co-researcher, co-designer, co-innovator, and co-practitioner**.
- all partners **bring with them their own domain and expertise**, positioned as equally indispensable for and usable for all and for the research & innovation process.

3 Requirement 3: Cross-sectorial collaboration within transformative partnerships

Within the EPIC-WE QH, partners work together in close and continuous cross-sectorial co-creation to develop transformative QH partnerships and joint practices in cultural innovation.

- **On the macro level:** In order to think and talk together, the QH partners take joint decisions, collaborate on shared aims, objectives and outcomes and establish a common vocabulary and understanding.
- **On the meso level:** In order to be and act together, the QH form local hubs that meet monthly to ensure joint development of principles and protocols for cultural innovation
- **On the micro level:** In order to operationalise 'cultural innovations' through concrete everyday practices, the quadruple helix co-organise events and activities where all helix partners meet in the middle to test and evaluate cultural innovation formats, methods and processes.

However, meeting the other(s) halfway is hard work to 'embrace the culturally alien' through continuously stabilising what is culturally unstable and destabilising what is culturally stable through collectively reimagining, reconfiguring, and revitalising new culture(s) in the middle.

3 Requirement 3: Inhabit Living Labs as vibrant cultural homes

- **Cultural Hubs are 'cultural homes'** for the coming together of the QH partners. They function as vibrant in vivo cultural environments.
- This requires **real-world, real-life sites of culture** wherein cultural practices naturally unfold as part of everyday cultural life. This could be museums, public spaces, libraries, cultural centres, cultural heritage sites, creative industries or other '**living cultures**' within which the Cultural Hub can find a home and unfold.
- However, **the idea is not to 'overpower'** or assimilate the existing cultural ecosystem. But to ideate and co-design cultural transformation with present/future sites and inhabitants.

4 Requirement 4 Cultivating Mode 3 cultural knowledge & innovation cultures

The EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem aim towards reciprocal value creation. It should create both value for each individual helix partner and value creation for the combined helices as they join forces in the middle:

- A QH has **internal tensions and differences** when it comes to what counts as good knowledge, methods, practices, outcomes, and value.
- Consequently, **the whole should be greater than the sum of its parts** and be something partners cannot accomplish on their own. Otherwise, it is not worth the effort.
- **If any helix domain were excluded, the aimed-for cultural innovation would become impossible.** Only through the co-existence, co-evolution, and co-specialisation of the four domains, will cultural innovation in QH Cultural Hubs become possible.

4 Requirement 4 Practice Living Labs for empowered participation in culture

The goal of **Cultural Hubs are to provide environments for empowered participation** – collectively and individually. To position each QH partner as an indispensable and equal contributor within the Cultural Hub.

Cultural Hubs flourish when their QH partners flourish and feel ‘at home’ respected and acknowledged – this is what Cultural Hubs are to be evaluated on.

The QH partnership – and the Cultural Hub – **must resonate with cultural curiosity, creative imagination, empowered agency, and valued communality** to make sense - especially when measured against the efforts, tensions, complexities, challenges and compromises each QH sector and partner is confronted with in the middle.

This is also what the EPIC-WE acronym stands for: ***Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments.***

4.2 The local and glocal EPIC-WE

The EPIC-WE project offers a profound opportunity to explore and evaluate cultural game jams within and across local QH Cultural Hubs, embracing the intersection of global and local perspectives in glocal cultural innovation. The first round of interventions addressed specific local cultural and societal challenges, providing a grounded context for deeper engagement. Moving forward, the second round aims to delve into "glocal" cultural game jams, where global and local elements dynamically influence and shape one another – through shared themes, cross-integrations of Youth Advisory Board perspectives, through shared communication environments with the participating youth, and in utilising the same protocols for cultural game jam design, intervention, and evaluation. This fusion highlights the richness and complexity of cultural exchange. It is informed by emerging trends in the literature on glocalisation—particularly in the context of game development, which underscores the significance of navigating the interplay between global tendencies and local cultures, offering pathways for innovation and cultural sustainability across cultures, sites, networks, and people.

The QH Cultural Hubs within the EPIC-WE project are approaching the design and implementation of glocal game jams, working across QH Cultural Hubs while utilising insights and models from D3.2 protocol 1-4. These cultural game jams are co-created to foster transdisciplinary and transnational collaboration, co-creation, and cultural exchange while emphasising the integration of local traditions and cultures with globally relevant and contemporary themes and problems. By combining shared challenges, themes, design considerations and values, and collaborative approaches—synchronous and asynchronous—the project ensures that youth are empowered to engage and contribute meaningfully to these processes. This approach bridges local and global contexts and positions cultural game jams as a platform for innovation that respects and amplifies diverse cultural narratives. EPIC-WE contributes to developing more interconnected and resilient innovation ecosystems through this inclusive process as an 'epic we': a collective, cooperative, and caring innovation partnership.

CONCLUSION

05

5. Conclusion

This report has presented the foundational principles and practical sector, glocal, and local dimensions of the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs.

By summarising the theoretical frameworks of first the Triple Helix (TH), then the Quadruple Helix Ecosystem, and lastly, the Living Lab model introduced and thoroughly described in D3.1, Protocol 1 (initial report), D3.2, Protocol 1 (final report) has transformed this initial concepts, frameworks and models into EPIC-WE researched grounded and practice evaluated guiding principles for the macro-level design of the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs providing QH partners with collaborative local-glocal environments for cross-sector cultural research and innovation. These QH Cultural Hubs serve as real-world models and environments for partners to co-create cultural innovations, such as Cultural Game Jams (CGJs), fostering transformative partnerships and meetings in the middle.

A critical aspect has been the joint and iterative materialisation of shared approaches and practices throughout developing the EPIC-WE Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and Cultural Hubs.

Through the first round of DRB interventions, the EPIC-WE project has made significant strides in developing and refining the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs. EPIC-WE has successfully connected diverse sector participants in co-creating innovation and research partnerships carried out across three European sites: Hilversum, Aarhus, and Óbidos. These interventions have combined practical testing and evaluation with iterative research, design, and construction, resulting in a robust foundation of knowledge and practices for Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems and QH Cultural Hubs. The concept of 'meeting in the middle' has been central to forming these transformative partnerships in cultural research and innovation. This approach has been further substantiated by and evolved through the interplay of local, glocal, and sectoral dimensions, which continuously intertwine each other – especially in the helix partners' cross-sector, cross-hub collaborative endeavours.

Significantly, D3.2, “Protocol 1 on Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation: EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and QH Cultural Hubs (final report),” contributes to the foundational principles for developing, implementing, and operationalising the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and Cultural Hubs. Combined, these lead to the core contribution of the report: the EPIC-WE model for QH Cultural Hubs and its 2 x 4 requirements.

Taken together, QH Cultural Innovation seeks to co-shape new cultural futures, reimagine European values and heritage, and innovate cultural products through cultural game jams and game-making as culture-making towards the revitalisation of cultural heritage and the experience of empowered participation in culture.

The report outlines the foundational principles for QH Cultural Hubs, which include democratising cultural innovation by including citizens and users as core partners, forming equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation, instituting meetings in the middle, practising co-creative cultural innovation and transformation for the public good(s), developing real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs, and advancing empowered participation in culture.

Looking towards the future, the extension of the initial D3.1, Protocol 1 report in the final D3.2, Protocol 1 report here, will lead to further conceptualisations, implementations, explorations, and evaluations of the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs in the remaining period of the project (2025-2026) resulting in the final visualised publishing of these on the [EPIC-WE Resource Website](#). Finally, as a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action emphasising horizontal integration of knowledge and innovation, the approaches and conceptualisations presented in this report have been evaluated, iterated, and reinforced by the knowledge and experiences produced in the project and through its cross-sector, cross-hub, and cross-disciplinary operationalisation. This includes its [Prisma2020 Systematic Literature Review, research protocol](#), 12 Design-Based Research interventions, empirical studies within, across, and beyond the project's Work Packages, Cultural Game Jams, QH Cultural Hubs, and cross-sector partnerships in EPIC-WE.

Overall, the EPIC-WE project outcomes of the QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs offer a significant contribution to the field of cultural innovation in cross-sector partnerships. The project's emphasis on cultural co-creation, cross-sector collaboration, transformative partnerships, meetings in the middle, open knowledge sharing, and empowered participation have resulted in a robust model for cross-sector, local and glocal cultural research and innovation.

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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